

Research Organization Registry Annual Report 2020

About this report

Hello!

We're excited to introduce the first-ever ROR Annual Report (a "ROR-port," if you will), meant to provide a helpful overview of everything ROR has been up to in the past year, an at-a-glance view of current activities, and a quick preview what's coming in the year ahead.

Questions or feedback? Contact info@ror.org.

Let's ROR!

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About ROR: aims & scope

- Focused specifically on **affiliations** in scholarly research
- Infrastructure designed to **connect organizations** to researchers and research outputs
- Developed with, by, and for the **community**
- **Open** and **noncommercial**

ROR is a community-led registry of open, sustainable, usable, and unique identifiers for every research organization in the world.

About ROR: evolution

Since the ROR minimum viable registry (MVR) launched in 2019, ROR has been in a startup phase focused on building the foundations for long-term sustainability and success. This includes working with GRID to build off the initial seed data for ROR, securing resourcing, strengthening and developing core infrastructure, and driving adoption of ROR.

2016–
2018

Exploratory phase

17 organizations collaborate to define core vision & basic requirements for open community registry of organization identifiers.

2019

Launch of ROR MVR

CDL, Crossref, DataCite, and Digital Science build and lead launch of ROR MVR, using seed data from GRID.

2020

Setting ROR up for success

ROR team defines working governance model, outlines resourcing plan, engages with early adopters.

2021

Expanding ROR

Focus on strengthening core infrastructure, expanding adoption, launching processes for independent curation of registry data.

About ROR: service model

The ROR service model encompasses two primary components:

Open registry of IDs and metadata

- Crosswalks to GRID, ISNI, Wikidata, Crossref Funder IDs

Open tools for interacting with the registry

- API, Search, Data dump, Reconciler

As of December 2020, the registry had 99,609 ROR IDs and associated metadata records

The screenshot shows the ROR registry interface. At the top left is the ROR logo. A search bar contains the text "Search Registry...". To the right are links for "ABOUT" and "SCORE". Below the search bar, it displays "99,609 Organizations". A search result is shown for the URL "https://ror.org/0397tsa92". The organization name is "Clark Atlanta University" with the acronym "CAU". Under "WEBSITE", the URL "http://www.cau.edu/" is listed. Under "OTHER IDENTIFIERS", the following are shown: GRID grid.254275.3, ISNI 0000000122243669, and Wikidata Q4572296. At the bottom, there are two tags: "UNITED STATES" and "EDUCATION".

About ROR: structure & governance

ROR is operated as a **cross-organization collaboration**. It is not an independent organization by design.

ROR seeks to achieve **community-based governance** through its steering group, advisory group, and working groups.

About ROR: sustainability model

- Collaborative leadership by trusted and stable organizations in the research infrastructure space
- Low overhead, focused scope
- Early and broad community engagement and adoption
- Diversified resourcing (grants, donations, in-kind funds) during startup phase (2019 to ~2022)

ROR is sustainable because it is being led by trusted and stable organizations, supported by the community, and because it is a lean and nimble operation.¹

About ROR: Resourcing

ROR is resourced through in-kind contributions and external funding (community contributions and grants)

ROR's governing organizations commit both dedicated and ad hoc personnel resources to ROR. For 2020–2021, these commitments are outlined in the table to the right.

Governing organizations also provide additional services such as accounting (Crossref), web hosting (DataCite), grants administration (CDL), and curation support (CDL).

Personnel resourcing, 2020–2021

Resource	Type	%	Source
Project lead	Dedicated	.50	CDL
Technical lead	Dedicated	.50	Crossref
Adoption manager	Dedicated	.50	DataCite
Technical support	Ad hoc	.20	Crossref & DataCite
Outreach support	Ad hoc	.20	Crossref & DataCite

About ROR: Resourcing

At the end of 2019, ROR set a fundraising goal to secure \$400K (USD) in external funds by the end of 2021 through a combination of grants and community contributions.

By mid-2020, ROR had already exceeded this goal. These funds give ROR stable footing to pursue key projects during this startup phase to set ROR up for longer-term success.

External funds, 2020–2022

Source	Amount (USD)
Community contributions	\$104K
IMLS grant	\$247K
NSF EAGER grant	\$200K
Totals	\$551K

Looking back on 2020 and looking ahead to 2021

In 2020, ROR focused on stabilizing its operations, securing resourcing, and engaging with early adopters.

In 2021, ROR is focused on expanding adoption, defining a longer-term sustainability and governance model, and implementing independent curation of the registry.

2020 highlights

2020 was a year in which ROR began gaining wider recognition and visibility. ROR strengthened its resourcing and began working to drive adoption across the community.

Recognition

ROR added to United States Library of Congress list of Standard Identifiers²

ROR recommended as “standard” persistent identifier for organizations by key stakeholders³

ROR commits to following Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI)⁴

Resourcing

ROR obtains funding from the National Science Foundation (NSF)⁵ and Institute for Museum and Library Studies (IMLS)⁶ to drive adoption and develop a curation model over the next 2 years

Fundraising through grants and community donations exceeds 2019–2021 goal

ROR team adds technical lead and adoption lead

Adoption

Adoption working group formed

Initial adoption strategy developed

Many integrations emerging in the community

2021 focus areas

In 2021, ROR is focusing on expanding and supporting ROR integrations, strengthening its core infrastructure, and laying the groundwork for long-term sustainability.

Adoption/Integration

Integration tools, resources, best practices

API enhancements

API/adoption metrics & dashboards

Interoperability with other identifiers & PID services

Infrastructure

Support location data and relationships in ROR metadata

Support independent additions and updates to the registry

Implement community-based curation workflows

Sustainability

Develop long-term resourcing plan for ROR

Continue to engage community members in governance, development, and adoption

About the ROR Community

ROR is a community-led registry of research organization identifiers and metadata. ROR seeks to provide an open and community-driven solution to the problem of identifying research organizations and connecting them to research outputs.

The ROR Community⁷ is a broad group of stakeholders interested in supporting ROR and/or using ROR IDs in their work.

ROR community group at a glance

The ROR community group is a voluntary group for those interested in supporting and using ROR. Members meet for bimonthly update calls and participate in specialized working groups. As of December 2020, the group had 85 members.

Members by organization type

Members by country

2020 ROR Community Survey Results

In November 2020, the first ROR Community Survey was circulated. The aim is to run a similar survey on an annual basis to understand the broader landscape of ROR stakeholders and their needs.

The 2020 survey received 179 responses.

What type of organization do you represent?

Survey respondents represented a range of different organizations.

Where are you located?

Survey respondents came from a range of geographic regions, primarily Europe and Canada/United States.

What are your reasons for being interested in ROR?

Survey respondents indicated a range of reasons for being interested in ROR.

Have you used the following ROR tools and services?

Many respondents have used ROR search, but fewer respondents have used the ROR API and other tools. Many respondents have not used any tools and/or do not know how to use them. This is an opportunity for more outreach and guidance.

Rate your knowledge of the following aspects of ROR

More than 50% of respondents indicated some knowledge about ROR’s aims and scope, ways to get involved, and ROR integrations.

More than 50% indicated lack of knowledge of ROR’s sustainability model, governance, roadmap, and how the registry is updated.

These results suggest that more outreach and communications about ROR’s activities in these areas is needed.

Is your organization planning to integrate ROR?

Plans to integrate ROR among respondents' organizations are mixed. Many organizations are planning to integrate or have already integrated ROR. Many are also unsure of their plans to do so. A few organizations do not plan to integrate.

How would ROR be useful to you/your organization?

There are a number of ways in which ROR is seen to be useful. The most common reasons indicated by respondents were disambiguation and research tracking.

How important are the following aspects of ROR?

The majority of respondents indicated that every aspect of ROR was important or very important. Providing open data and infrastructure and having long-term sustainability ranked highest in importance.

Who is adopting ROR? Where and how are ROR IDs being integrated?

ROR adoption is a key area of focus in 2021 and beyond. ROR IDs are already being used in various ways⁸ and we are interested in capturing the current landscape of adoption and working with adopters to help them achieve their goals.

Integration workflows

Community integrations of ROR typically fall into three categories.

In 2021, ROR will be focused on how to further drive and support various integrations. This work includes forming an API users group, developing dashboards to track adoption, defining best practices, and developing tools to support adoption and use of ROR IDs.

DISAMBIGUATE ORGANIZATIONS

Using ROR API/dataset

PRODUCE METADATA

With ROR IDs included

CONSUME METADATA

With ROR IDs included

Integration highlights

In the past year, new integrations have emerged among a wide range of communities and system types.

PUBLISHERS

OJS,
Rockefeller
University
Press,
Hindawi

INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS

DataCite,
Crossref
(coming soon!),
ORCID
(coming soon!)

OA PUBLISHING AGREEMENT SUPPORT

Unsub,
Journal
Checker Tool,
OA
Switchboard

GRANT MANAGEMENT & COMPLIANCE

Proposal
Central,
Chronos Hub

REPOSITORIES

Dryad,
British Library

ROR in the wild

Here are some examples of ROR IDs spotted in the wild in recent integrations.

Unsub

The Unsub interface displays a profile for "Demo University". It includes a header with the Unsub logo and the university name. Below the header, there is a section for "Group members (1)" with a list of members, including "liz@demo.edu(you) Admin". There is also a section for "ROR IDs (1)" showing a "demo ROR ID" of "00xbe3815".

OJS

The OJS interface shows "User Details" for a user. It includes a text input field for the "Homepage URL" and a dropdown menu for "Affiliation". The dropdown menu is open, showing "University of Bern [https://ror.org/02k7v4d05]" and "Université de Berne". Below the dropdown, there is a text input field for the "Affiliation" containing "University of Wisconsin-Madison" and a text input field for the "ROR ID" containing "https://ror.org/01y2jtd41".

Journal Checker Tool

The Journal Checker Tool interface displays a dark-themed screen with the question "Is this compliant with Plan S?". Below the question, there are three categories: "JOURNAL", "MY FUNDER", and "MY INSTITUTION". Under "JOURNAL", there is a button for "Nature (Springer Science and Business Media LLC), ISSN: 1476-46". Under "MY FUNDER", there is a button for "Wellcome". Under "MY INSTITUTION", there is a button for "University of Wisconsin-Madison". At the bottom, there is a yellow button for "University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States of America (ROR:01y2jtd41)".

DataCite Fabrica

The DataCite Fabrica interface shows a dropdown menu for "Affiliation" with "University of Wisconsin-Madison" selected. Below the dropdown, there is a text input field for the "ROR ID" containing "https://ror.org/01y2jtd41". At the bottom, there is a note: "Affiliation names and identifiers are provided by the Research Organization Registry (ROR)."

References

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Credits

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Let's ROR together!

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